

REDUCED ORDER TECHNIQUES FOR MODELLING THE EFFECTS OF DAMAGE IN COMPOSITE PLATES

*Basem Suliman¹, Carol A. Featherston² and David Kennedy³

¹Cardiff University, School of Engineering, Queen's Buildings, The Parade, Cardiff, CF24 3AA, United Kingdom, SulimanBS@cardiff.ac.uk, www.cardiff.ac.uk

²Cardiff University, School of Engineering, Queen's Buildings, The Parade, Cardiff, CF24 3AA, United Kingdom, FeatherstonCA@cardiff.ac.uk, www.cardiff.ac.uk

³Cardiff University, School of Engineering, Queen's Buildings, The Parade, Cardiff, CF24 3AA, United Kingdom, KennedyD@cardiff.ac.uk, www.cardiff.ac.uk

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ABSTRACT

During the early stages of aircraft design, fast and reliable analysis tools are required to process the large numbers of alternative configurations and load cases which need to be considered. Finite element analysis (FEA) is capable of handling many combinations of loading and boundary conditions for different cases of damages but at high modelling and computational cost. These costs are reduced significantly in the exact strip method. This technique provides an efficient alternative approach using an exact dynamic stiffness matrix based on a continuous distribution of stiffness and mass over a structure composed of composite plates, so avoiding the discretization to nodal points that is implicit in FE analysis. However due to its prismatic requirements, the exact strip method can model damaged plates directly only if the damaged region stretches along the whole length of the plate. A novel combination of exact strip method and finite element theory denoted VFM that can be used to improve the ability of this approach to model more complex cases of damaged plates is introduced. The capability and efficiency of the hybrid method is proved based on comparisons made with pure FEA and a previous technique based on the exact strip method.

1 Introduction

Minimizing the mass of an aircraft's structure through the use of composites reduces the cost of materials and manufacturing, as well as fuel consumption and atmospheric emissions. Delamination is one of the most frequent causes of failure in composite laminate structures, particularly those subjected to compressive loads. Delaminations reduce overall stiffness and can grow rapidly under postbuckling loads potentially leading to sudden structural failure[1]. They can also cause significant reductions in the associated natural frequencies of the structure. Many researchers have investigated the effects of damage on the buckling or vibration behaviour of composite structures. Pekbey and Sayman [2], Lee and Park [1] and Cappello and Tumino [3] studied the interaction between local and global buckling and the location and size of the delamination. Pre- and post-buckling behaviour of a delaminated composite laminate was examined by Karihaloo and Stang [4] who introduced guidelines for assessing the threat posed by interlaminar matrix delamination. Liu et al. [5] explored the postbuckling behaviour of flat composite plates with two through-the-width delaminations under compressive load.

In recent years, the majority of the research carried out in this field has used finite element (FE) analysis to model the laminates incorporating one or more damaged regions. The FE method provides a versatile approach, capable of handling many combinations of load and boundary conditions for a range of damage shapes. However, even with today's computer hardware, this type of analysis still often comes at a high computational cost. During an aircraft's preliminary design stage when many alternative configurations and load cases need to be considered, fast and reliable analysis tools are required. The exact strip method [6] provides an efficient alternative approach using an exact dynamic stiffness matrix based on a continuous distribution of stiffness and mass over the structure, so avoiding the discretization

to nodal points that is implicit in FE analysis. However due to its prismatic requirements, the exact strip method can model damaged plates directly only if the damaged region stretches along the whole length of the plate. The aim of this study is to introduce a novel technique which can be used to improve the ability of this approach to model more complex cases of damaged plates. This approach is a novel combination of exact strip method and finite element theory, denoted VFM. For validation purposes and demonstrating the efficiency of this technique, a comparison is made with pure FEA and a smearing technique based on exact strip method presented by Damghani et al.[7].

2 Theory and formulation used in VFM ψ

Damghani et al. [8] studied the critical buckling of composite plates with through-the-length delaminations using exact stiffness analysis and an iterative search known as the Wittrick–Williams algorithm [9]. The exact theory assumes sinusoidal buckling or vibration mode shapes in the longitudinal direction, with all three components of the displacement varying sinusoidally along any longitudinal line with a half-wavelength λ which divides exactly into the plate length l . This is illustrated in Figure 1 which shows the perturbation edge displacements and nodal lines of a plate during buckling or vibration. Edge displacements are multiplied by $\exp(i\pi x/\lambda) * \cos(2\pi n t)$, where n is the frequency. This approach was implemented in the computer program VIPASA [10].

Figure 1: Perturbation edge displacements, and nodal lines of a plate.

However in cases where in-plane shear loading is present and the mode is skewed, the desired support conditions will not be satisfied, limiting the applicability of the software. In these instances a VICON (VIPasa with CONstraints) analysis is utilized [11]. The key difference between VICON and VIPASA analysis is that VICON introduces Lagrangian multipliers to couple responses at different values of half-wavelength λ in order to satisfy constraints such as simply supported end conditions [12]. The VICON stiffness matrix comprises a series of VIPASA stiffness matrices and assumes that the deflections of an infinitely long plate can be expressed as a Fourier series λ

$$\mathbf{D}_a = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \mathbf{D}_m \exp(i\pi x/\lambda_m) \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{D}_a is the nodal displacement amplitude vector of the plate assembly, \mathbf{D}_m are the displacement amplitude vectors from a series of VIPASA analyses,

$$\lambda_m = \frac{l}{\xi + 2m}, (m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots, \pm q) \quad (2)$$

and the plate structure is assumed to have a mode shape that repeats at intervals of $L = 2l/\xi$ where the parameter ξ takes any value in the range $0 \leq \xi \leq 1$. The perturbation force vectors \mathbf{P}_a are similarly defined as

$$\mathbf{P}_a = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_m \exp(i\pi x/\lambda_m) \quad (3)$$

The VICON stiffness equations relating \mathbf{P}_m , \mathbf{D}_m and the Lagrangian multipliers \mathbf{P}_L are thus expressed as

$$\begin{bmatrix} l\mathbf{K}_0 & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{E}_0^H \\ \mathbf{0} & l\mathbf{K}_1 & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{E}_1^H \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & l\mathbf{K}_{-1} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{E}_{-1}^H \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & l\mathbf{K}_2 & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{E}_2^H \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & l\mathbf{K}_{-2} & \dots & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{E}_{-2}^H \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \ddots & \mathbf{E}_n \\ \mathbf{E}_0 & \mathbf{E}_1 & \mathbf{E}_{-1} & \mathbf{E}_2 & \mathbf{E}_{-2} & \dots & \mathbf{E}_n & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{D}_0 \\ \mathbf{D}_1 \\ \mathbf{D}_{-1} \\ \mathbf{D}_2 \\ \mathbf{D}_{-2} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{D}_n \\ \mathbf{P}_L \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P}_0 \\ \mathbf{P}_1 \\ \mathbf{P}_{-1} \\ \mathbf{P}_2 \\ \mathbf{P}_{-2} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{P}_n \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The stiffness matrix in Eq. (4) may be partitioned as

$$\mathbf{K}_{VICON} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{Global\ VIPASA} & \mathbf{C}^H \\ \mathbf{C} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where

$$\mathbf{K}_{Global\ VIPASA} = \begin{bmatrix} l\mathbf{K}_0 & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & l\mathbf{K}_1 & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & l\mathbf{K}_{-1} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & l\mathbf{K}_2 & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & l\mathbf{K}_{-2} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \ddots \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{C} = [\mathbf{E}_0 \quad \mathbf{E}_1 \quad \mathbf{E}_{-1} \quad \mathbf{E}_2 \quad \mathbf{E}_{-2} \quad \dots \quad \dots] \quad (7)$$

and superscript H denotes Hermitian transpose. $\mathbf{K}_{Global\ VIPASA}$ is a series of VIPASA matrices \mathbf{K}_m at different values of λ_m and \mathbf{C} is the global constraint matrix comprising submatrices \mathbf{E}_m . Details of how the \mathbf{E}_m can be calculated are given by Anderson et al. [11].

This work was extended by Damghani et al. [7] to cover non-prismatic scenarios including composite plates with embedded rectangular delaminations through the introduction of a smearing method (SM) in which the non-prismatic portion of the structure is replaced by an equivalent prismatic portion whose component strips have equal length l as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Sketch of the VICON model for a laminate of length l , width B and thickness h , having an embedded rectangular delamination of length $d (= \mu l)$ and width b , reproduced from [7].

In this paper, embedded delaminations are modelled more accurately using a novel combination of VICON and FE. This approach uses FE analysis to model the longitudinal portion of the plate containing the damage as shown in Figure 3, and VICON analysis to more efficiently model the remainder of the plate. The Wittrick-Williams algorithm is used to find the critical buckling loads and natural frequencies for the damaged plates. Thus VICON is used to calculate the dynamic stiffness matrices for the undamaged regions, while the FE method is used to calculate the static stiffness and mass matrices for the damaged rectangular strip. Embedded damage is modelled by including elements with different stiffness properties within this strip.

Figure 3: VICON and FE method (VFM) modelling damaged plate

The hybrid dynamic stiffness matrix of the plate is formed by using Lagrangian multipliers to couple the VICON and FE components, as follows.

$$\mathbf{K}_{Global} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{Global VIPASA} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{C}_1^H \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{K}_{FE} & \mathbf{C}_2^T \\ \mathbf{C}_1 & \mathbf{C}_2 & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Here, the constraint matrices \mathbf{C}_1 and \mathbf{C}_2 enforce equal displacements and rotations at the nodes connecting the undamaged and damaged strips. \mathbf{C}_1 also includes any support conditions in the undamaged regions. \mathbf{C}_2^T is the transpose of \mathbf{C}_2 . \mathbf{K}_{FE} is the FE dynamic stiffness matrix for the damaged rectangular strip. In the case of vibration problems \mathbf{K}_{FE} takes the form

$$\mathbf{K}_{FE} = \mathbf{k} - n^2 \mathbf{m} \quad (9)$$

where n is the frequency, \mathbf{k} and \mathbf{m} are the static stiffness matrix and equivalent mass matrix of the damaged rectangular strip. The basic equations used for the calculation of \mathbf{k} and \mathbf{m} are detailed by Przemieniecki [13].

3 Numerical results

A study has been made of the natural frequencies of plates containing through-the-length and embedded damage, including delaminations and areas of reduced stiffness of different sizes and severities, using VFM, SM, VICON analysis and the FE software ABAQUS [14]. Figure 4 illustrates the case of a composite plate containing centrally located through-the-length and embedded rectangular damage.

Figure 4: Composite plate containing centrally located through-the-length and embedded rectangular damage.

Figure 5 details the results of analyses for isotropic plates having length $l=100\text{mm}$, width $b=100\text{mm}$, and thickness $h=1\text{mm}$. They have material properties of Young's modulus $E=110\text{ kN}\cdot\text{mm}^{-2}$, density $\rho=2300\text{ kg/mm}^3$ and Poisson's ratio $\nu=0.3$ with two values of stiffness reduction factor for the damaged region considered: $f=0.67$, $f=0.75$. VFM, ABAQUS and VICON are used for analysing through-the-length damaged isotropic plate. The graph (5(a)) shows a near perfect match between VICON and ABAQUS when handling this kind of damage. For $0 < \beta/b < 0.4$, VFM is also seen to perfectly match these results. However, as the damage width increases ($\beta/b > 0.4$), VFM gives higher results than both VICON and ABAQUS albeit with a maximum difference of only 1.55% at $\beta/b=1$. This is due to the number of elements used in the finite element part of the VFM model and hence the number of constraints applied being slightly too small leading to the model being over constrained and as a result of this raising the natural frequencies. The graph (5 (b)) presents the first natural frequencies of an isotropic plate containing embedded rectangular damage, as calculated using VFM, ABAQUS and SM. Excellent agreement between VFM and ABAQUS in modelling the embedded damage is demonstrated.

This is a significant improvement on the previous smearing method which gives good results when the damaged plate vibrates globally, $0 < \beta/b < 0.3$, but conservative results when the plate vibrates locally, $\beta/b > 0.3$, since this mode is not adequately represented.

Figure 5: Plots of lowest natural frequency of isotropic plates (ω_1) against width β/b of centrally located damage using the three techniques, Smearing Method (SM), ABAQUS and VFM. (a) through-the-length damage and $f=0.75$. (b) embedded rectangular damage, damage length (d) = 50mm and $f=0.67$.

Figure 6 compares the first natural frequencies for a delaminated composite plate, for delaminations of length $l=100$ mm, width $b=100$ mm, thickness $h=3$ mm, two different delamination depths and material properties Young's moduli $E_1=110$ kNmm⁻², $E_2=10$ kNmm⁻², shear moduli $G_{12}=G_{13}=G_{23}=5$ kNmm-

2, Poisson's ratio $\nu_{12}=0.33$ and density $\rho=4480\text{ kg/mm}^3$. The composite comprises 12 plies of thickness 0.25mm in the sequence [0/90/0/0/90/0]S. Plates are examined using VFM, ABAQUS and SM. Figures 6 (a) and (b) show very good agreement between VFM and ABAQUS for both delamination depths with maximum differences between VFM and ABAQUS results of 1.95% and 4.6% for delamination depths of $h/4$ and $h/2$ respectively occurring when $\beta/b = 1$. In these cases, VFM uses finite element theory only to model the damaged plates, since the damage extends across the whole plate, see Figure 3. This results in an increasing error as the finite elements become larger. In terms of the SM results, as stated previously, the embedded rectangular damage is modelled indirectly, see Figure 2. As seen in Figure 6(a), when $0 < \beta/b < 0.4$ the SM gives slightly higher predictions of the natural frequencies because it does not capture the increasing localised effects, whereas when $\beta/b > 0.4$ the SM method predicts a more conservative local behaviour not seen in the VFM and ABAQUS models. As the delamination depth is moved to the mid-thickness (Figure 6 (b)), SM predicts only global vibration for all cases of delamination sizes and hence shows better agreement with the other techniques.

Figure 6: Plots of lowest natural frequency of composite plates (ω_1) against width β/b for centrally located 50mm long embedded rectangular delaminations, using the three techniques, Smearing Method (SM), ABAQUS and VFM. (a) delamination depth = $h/4$. (b) delamination depth = $h/2$.

Figure 7: VFM, ABAQUS and Smearing Method plots of first natural frequency mode for a composite plate with an embedded rectangular delamination of $\beta/b=0.5$

The computational efficiency of the VICON analysis has been demonstrated Anderson et al. [11] but this can only be used when the damage is through-the-length. VFM is capable of handling both through-the-length and embedded damage efficiently. Excellent agreement is seen between VFM and FE (ABAQUS) for all cases of damage studied with significantly reduced calculation times for VFM against FE. Figure 7 shows plots of the first natural frequency mode for a composite plate containing a centrally located embedded rectangular delamination of $d=50\text{mm}$ and $b=50\text{mm}$. The three techniques generally give the same mode shape with the out of plane displacements within the delamination region being slightly higher than those in an undamaged plate. The maximum difference in the magnitude of the out of plane displacement between ABAQUS and VFM is 3%.

4 Conclusions

In conclusion, VFM is based on a concept that allows the exact strip method to work along with finite element theory to enable the modelling of more complex geometries of damage. To prove the effectiveness of this method, composite and isotropic plates containing through the length and embedded rectangular damage and delamination have been examined. VFM has been shown to efficiently handle geometries of damage that the previous VICON models could not. It also shows improved agreement with finite element analysis when compared with the smearing method previously proposed which whilst giving good results in a computationally efficient manner for cases of damage where the plates vibrate globally, gives conservative results where the plate undergoes local vibration due to the way in which embedded damage is modelled.

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